

How Advanced Power Electronics Can Accelerate the Diffusion of Energy Storage?

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Abstract

This paper focuses on an innovative advanced power electronics device (PED) with integrated storage management capabilities that is being developed within the Horizon 2020 project RESOLVD. To start with, the technology behind the devices is described together with its key functionalities. The paper proceeds by referring to key stakeholders that may benefit from the solution and explains the motivations and implementation possibilities for various stakeholder groups. Based upon well composed narratives, the stakeholders are classified according to two different sets of mapping dimensions: Power-Interest-Attitude and Power-Urgency-Legitimacy. The performed stakeholder analysis suggests that the PED can, besides its primer use by distribution system operators, be attractive for various low-voltage grid users. The versatile operation and design of the PED make it a key technology for the modernization and decarbonization of the low-voltage distribution grids and a profitable business environment for the RESOLVD solution is envisioned.

Introduction and Background

With an increasing number of distributed renewable energy sources installed at various ends of the low-voltage grid challenges arise with respect to ensuring security and quality of supply. Combining local renewable generation with local energy storage capacities can mitigate those challenges. Yet, an increasing market for storage with dropping costs of the various storage solutions can be demanding, as batteries with different schedules of charging and discharging must be managed simultaneously. However, technological innovation can well respond to that issue.

Within the H2020 Project RESOLVD (2017–2020) an innovative advanced power electronics device (PED) with integrated storage management capabilities is being developed. The device will be capable of optimizing on the co-joint charging and discharging schedules of different storage technologies. In this way the device will allow for significantly improved grid-to-storage interactions and will contribute for better control and flexibility utilization in the low-voltage grid, based on flattening the demand curve at the substation level, loss reduction, improved voltage control and supply quality.

More specifically, the new PED embraces a variety of new technology – a modular power conversion system operated by an innovative intelligent local energy manager to cater for communications and for implementation of the overall device control logic. These new technologies will be supported by a decision support toolkit, a distributed software platform and a wide area monitoring system to comprise an overall solution that successfully supports the low-voltage grid.

The advanced PED is to facilitate interactions with legacy systems which makes it suitable for integration at various low-voltage grid levels. Thus, a diverse set of new business models can be envisioned to provide for an optimal utilization of energy storage capacities located at the premises of various stakeholders.

Material and Methods

As previously introduced, the PED to be produced in RESOLVD embraces a variety of new technologies including a modular power conversion system managed by an intelligent local energy manager (ILEM hereinafter) to cater for the communications and of the implementation of the overall device control logic. These new technologies will be integrated into an innovative distributed software platform and a wide area monitoring system managing the low-voltage grid. A basic understanding of the technology is an important prerequisite for evaluating the stakeholders' capability of taking it in use and for making references to relevant use cases.

The basic features of the novel PED are graphically depicted in Figure 1. As shown, the device is equipped with a heterogeneous grouping of battery types, composed by high performance lithium-ion battery packs and low-cost lead-acid ones. Thus, the system becomes a hybrid energy storage device. To exploit the main benefits of such hybridization, each battery pack is connected to a separate module of a power electronics-based power conversion system. The modularity of power electronics provides the device with high reliability and design flexibility.

At the time of receiving a power demand from the distributed software platform, the ILEM distributes it among the different battery packs according to their capabilities and state. Such action is performed by an innovative optimization algorithm inside ILEM named as power sharing algorithm. The power sharing algorithm takes into account the specificities of the batteries such as efficiency, energy storage and power capacities, cyclability, admissible charging and discharging rates, among others. Thus, it ensures the proper management of the heterogeneous grouping of the battery packs, exploiting in this way the main performance of each one. As a result, and in response to a step-profiled power demand from the distributed software platform, for instance, the ILEM (through its embedded power sharing algorithm) may determine to rapidly discharge lithium-ion packs, taking advantage of the remarkable admissible current rates and low degradation of this technology. After such a rapid response, the power sharing algorithm may slowly and progressively activate the lead-acid packs to provide a sustained power injection in time, minimizing their degradation.

Figure 1. The novel PED with heterogenous storage and its interaction with the management of the network.

The exploitation of the benefits of hybrid storages is one of the main technological challenges tackled in the RESOLVD project with respect to the design of the PED. Such innovative approach aims to answer the need of developing energy storage solutions for electrical networks with reduced cost and enhanced performance.

Apart from the hybridization aspect, other characteristics make the PED an advanced solution beyond the state-of-the-art. Those refer to the novel modular architecture of the power conversion system itself, and to the other management algorithms embedded into the ILEM. The ILEM provides the PED with high connectivity towards other agents of the network so as to provide services to the grid. These are based on exogenous control signals and remote measurements in either grid connected or isolated mode. The relevance of the ILEM is connoted while in grid isolated mode. In this situation, the PED is operated as a voltage source for the consumers connected nearby. The electrical stability and power quality of such a microgrid and the security of supply to consumers solely depend on the PED. In the same manner, the transition from grid-connected to isolated mode and vice versa, and the provision of anti-islanding protection to the associated neighborhood are services managed by the ILEM, thus providing added value to the PED. While in grid-connected mode, the ILEM may manage the energy storage capability of the PED so as to maximize the hosting capacity of distributed renewable generation for the connected neighborhood.

Having described the RESOLVD technology's concept, it is important to discuss the possibilities for market pick-up of the solution, given the specific stakeholder environment. Supporting market uptake of innovation and developing effective business models involves engaging affected stakeholders. Possible values which can be created by an innovation are key to understand the innovation's impact on stakeholders. RESOLVD's novel PED provides value to grid operators but could also be attractive to various other stakeholders. Identifying values for additional stakeholders would further boost market uptake of the solution.

To explore possible values, narrative building technique is used. Narrative building is qualitative method where storylines are developed to understand perspectives of various stakeholders. This work uses narratives to identify possible values for different types of stakeholders. A broad range of stakeholders from different market domains which could be affected by the innovation are selected. For each of the selected stakeholders a brief storyline is created on how the RESOLVD innovations can affect the stakeholders' businesses. These storylines form the narratives of different stakeholders and provide insight to their pain points and how these could be relieved using the PED, thereby revealing possible values for the stakeholders.

For the stakeholder analysis two maps are chosen, namely Power-Interest-Attitude map and Power-Urgency-Legitimacy map. Based upon the narratives, attributes like interests, attitude and urgency can be gauged and subsequent mapping can be done. Detailed explanation of the stakeholder mapping is out of scope of the current work and readers are referred to RESOLVD Deliverable D6.2.

Once values are identified using narratives, it is possible to create business models which define how value is created, delivered and captured (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). Value identification through narratives is the first step towards building new business models for PED. This is crucial for the success of the innovation and an important ongoing task within the RESOLVD project.

Results

Value identification through narratives

Table 1 provides narratives for few of the stakeholders identified. Readers who are interested in the exhaustive list of stakeholders are referred to RESOLVD Deliverable D6.2. Along with the narratives, the envisioned business motivation of each stakeholder is shown. The values for each stakeholder are revealed through the narratives. It should be noted that services from distributed software platform are required for scheduling the PED. These services can be requested to the DSO which owns the software

platform or the software can be owned by other stakeholders (e.g, SaaS or license). As it can be observed, the benefits for some stakeholders are not direct (e.g., for battery suppliers, for whom success of the power electronics device would mean more market demand for battery solutions). Such stakeholders do not directly benefit from the innovation but have complimentary benefits associated with its success. Thus, such stakeholders are prime candidates for being strategic partners in developing business for power electronics device. Some stakeholders would also feel threatened by the innovation as it would be competing with their products/solutions. Thus, through narratives it is also possible to identify the friction arising.

Table 1. Stakeholder narratives and motivation.

Stakeholders	Motivation	Narratives
DSO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better grid management • Improved reliability • Delaying upgrade investments • Flexibility services possible 	<p>DSO have multiple challenges while managing the grid, especially under growing distributed generation. PED can provide multiple values to DSO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevent congestion and over/under voltage issues • Voltage control through local reactive power injection • Improve power quality and reduce losses • Power management capabilities in intentional and controlled-island mode
Balance responsible parties (BRP), Balance service providers (BSP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimize imbalances 	<p>BRP have financial obligation to maintain production/consumption as committed in the market. BRP have contracts with the TSO for this obligation. In occurrence of imbalances, fines are levied or BRP take services from balance service providers at a cost. Flexibility facilitated through the PED could be used to reduce the imbalances at transmission levels when several PEDs are managed collaboratively.</p>
Local energy producers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved integration of renewable energy - increased profitability 	<p>PED can help in storing excess generation. PED can also allow effective grid connection of local energy producers in rural areas. PED together with distributed software platform and wide area monitoring system offers opportunity to plan resources in an efficient manner, improve profits by bidding in the market more accurately and a higher level of local energy integration using load scheduling.</p>
Energy communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased consumption from local energy resources • Improved grid reliability • Economic benefits from flexibility • Possibly lower electricity price/grid tariff 	<p>PED can enable local energy communities to better manage their resources, both generation and demand. Efficient management could also lead to reduced electricity tariffs. Such technologies provide information on when to activate flexibility using both storage and load scheduling. PED will enable energy communities to provide flexibility services to the DSO. Providing these flexibility services from PED will lower the payback period on the battery investment.</p>

Parking lot owners (or EV charging station owners)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower peaks resulting in lower connection charges • Lower energy costs • Reduce lead time to start operation 	<p>By investing in PED these stakeholders can reduce peaks and thus reduce connection charges (or use the same connection to charge more EVs). PED coupled with smart charging, using software applications, can reduce electricity bills. Most likely, actual management of charging will be outsourced to charge point operators as charging management is not the parking lot owners' core business. Charging station owners also face challenge of long waiting period for the grid to reinforce (or grid connection) before they could start operations. PED could thus reduce the lead time to start operation and provide early revenue generation opportunity for charging station owners.</p>
Charge point operators (CPO, responsible for smart charging)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of flexibility to reduce costs • Reduce lead time to start operation 	<p>CPO can either invest in PED to manage their customers' loads more economically or manage PED owned by their customers. Smart charging with PED could minimize electricity bills for charge point operators' customers. Critical events can be avoided and when such events occur PED could provide back-up and ability to operate in isolated mode. PED would enable charge point operators with competitive edge over their competitors. Depending upon ownership of the PED, the CPO could be customers or strategic partners.</p>
Prosumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher integration of self-generated electricity • Possibly lower electricity price/grid tariff 	<p>The PED can be an attractive innovation for larger prosumers. The narrative replicates the one of energy communities.</p>
Industries/ commercial buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher integration of self-generated electricity • Efficient energy management of facilities - reduced electricity costs • Green profiling 	<p>Dependent on the size but the narrative is similar to the one for energy communities.</p>
Battery manufacturers/ suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in battery sales 	<p>The PED will be a market facilitator for different batteries to realize their potential in the future smart grid. The ILEM, which is a top-layer management of the PED, could be used in other hybrid battery systems. Apart from this, the PED could be a solution for integrating second life batteries coming from the electromobility or stationary fields. More services from batteries means more revenues, thus making batteries a good investment case and further increasing market demand. Battery manufacturers can benefit by making their battery management system (BMS) open/compatible to the ILEM. Battery suppliers could package various batteries under the PED and provide better solutions to their customers.</p>

Energy service companies (ESCOs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased customer interest for investment in local storage/local generation 	PED with storage could allow ESCOs to provide flexibility services and increase the quality of services they offer. By providing flexibility the payback period of investments can be reduced (like investments in storage or rooftop PV). Direct benefit exists only when the ESCO decides to venture in providing flexibility services. Otherwise, benefits are indirect and the ESCOs would most likely partner with other relevant stakeholders for providing services to the DSO.
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Stakeholder mapping based upon narratives

By assessing attributes like interest, attitude and urgency through narratives, the two maps (Power-Interest-Attitude & Power-Urgency-Legitimacy) are created and a stakeholder analysis is performed. The two stakeholder maps are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Our analysis suggests that the PED with storage management capabilities can, besides its primer use by distribution system operators, be attractive for various low-voltage grid users. Among the most eminent ones are considered energy communities owning storage of various types, neighborhood/block managers, industrial facilities and commercial buildings of larger-scale. In addition, there are indirect beneficiaries of the innovation which would become promoters of the innovation and strategic partners for delivering the expected value. The narratives indicate a profitable business environment for the RESOLVD solution. However, possibilities for high degree of customization are needed and the overall applicability of the solution will depend on the market developments within the energy storage field.

Figure 2. Power-Interest-Attitude map of stakeholders based upon the narratives. Interest and attitude attributes are assessed through the narratives developed. Source: RESOLVD Deliverable D6.1.

Figure 3. Power-Urgency-Legitimacy map of stakeholder. The attribute of urgency is determined from the narratives. Source: RESOLVD Deliverable D6.2.

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Stakeholder mapping, derived from narratives, helped in selecting appropriate methods to engage different types of stakeholders based upon their salience. The stakeholder engagement strategies are out of the scope of this work and are described in RESOLVD Deliverable D6.2.

Discussion and Conclusions

This paper described the functionality of an advanced power electronics device to be developed in the RESOLVD project that will significantly improve grid-to-storage interactions, potentially resulting in flattening the demand curve at the substation level, loss reduction, improved voltage control and supply quality. Our research showed that the technology solution proves to be attractive for a variety of stakeholders who possess storage technology of various types and may serve as an excellent instrument for solving low-voltage grid challenges by helping DSO to operate the grid. Importantly, the device can contribute to solving the pending challenges of the low-voltage grid caused by distributed generation.

It could be the case that the stakeholders do not see the direct values as investigated through the narrative development technique. Thus, an important next step is to engage stakeholders and make them aware of the potential that the PED can provide to them. Initiatives for stakeholder engagement would

further reinforce identified values and eliminate values which are weak or not attractive. The process of stakeholder engagement could also reveal new values.

The stakeholder attributes which have been identified using qualitative method of narratives need to be validated. For validating the stakeholder mapping presented in this paper a stakeholder innovation group (SIG) has been established in the project. SIG contains crucial stakeholders as members from whom feedback will be taken to complete the analysis.

Considering the possibilities discussed in this paper, we recognize the vast potential of the RESOLVD PED and are grateful for being given the opportunity to work on this interesting topic within the RESOLVD project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 773715.

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